

- Abdelghafour, F.; Keresztes, B.; Germain, C.; Da Costa, J.-P. In Field Detection of Downy Mildew Symptoms with Proximal Colour Imaging. *Sensors* 2020, *20*, 4380.
- Adamides, G. , C. Katsanos , I. Constantinou, G. Christou, M., Xenos, T. Hadzilacos, Y. Edan. 2017. Design and development of a semi-autonomous agricultural vineyard sprayer: human-robot interaction aspects. *Journal of Field Robotics* 34(8): 1407-1426.
- Alia, O., Verlindena, B., Oudheusdena, D. V. 2009. Infield logistics planning for crop-harvesting operations. *Engineering Optimization*, 41(2), 183–197.
- Aguiar, A. S., dos Santos, F. N., Cunha, J. B., Sobreira, H., Sousa, A. J. 2020. Localization and Mapping for Robots in Agriculture and Forestry: A Survey. *Robotics*, 9(4), 97.
- Arad, B. , J. Balendonck, R. Barth, O. Ben-Shahar, Y. Edan, T. Hellstrom, J. Hemming, P. Kurtser, O. Ringdahl, T. Tielen, B. van Tuijl. 2020. Development of a Sweet Pepper Harvesting Robot. *Journal of Field Robotics*.
- Arad, B., P. Kurtser, E. Barnea, B. Harel, Y. Edan, O. Ben-Shahar. 2019. Controlled lighting and illumination-independent target detection for real-time cost-efficient applications. The case study of sweet pepper robotic harvesting. *Sensors* 19(6): 1390.
- Astuti, G., Giudice, G., Longo, D., Melita, C., Muscato, G., Orlando, A. (2009). An overview of the volcan project: An UAS for exploration of volcanic environments. *J. Intell. Robot. Syst.* 54:1-3.
- Bac, C.W., van Henten, E.J., Hemming, J., Edan, Y. 2014. Harvesting robots for high-value crops: state-of-the-art review and challenges ahead. *J. of Field Robotics* 31(6): 888–911.
- Bao, Y., Gai, J., Xiang, L., Tang, L. 2021. Field Robotic Systems for High-Throughput Plant Phenotyping: A Review and a Case Study. *High-Throughput Crop Phenotyping*, 13-38.
- Berenstein, R., Hočevár, M., Godeša, T., Edan, Y., Ben-Shahar, O. 2015. Distance-Dependent Multimodal Image Registration for Agriculture Tasks *Sensors* 15: 20845-62.
- Bernstein, R., O. Ben-Shahar, A. Shapiro, Y. Edan. 2010. Grape clusters and foliage detection algorithms for autonomous selective vineyard sprayer. *Intelligent Service Robotics* 3(4): 233-243.
- Bernstein, R. Y. Edan. 2017. Human-robot collaborative site-specific sprayer. *Journal of Field Robotics* 34(8): 1519–1530.

- Bezen, R., Halachmi, I. Edan, Y. 2020. Computer vision system for measuring individual cow intake using RGB-D camera and deep learning algorithms. *Computer and Electronics in Agriculture* 172: 105345.
- Bochtis, D. D., Vougioukas, S. G. 2008. Minimising the non-working distance travelled by machines operating in a headland field pattern. *Biosystems Engineering*, 101(1), 1–12.
- Bochtis, D. D., Sørensen, C. G., Vougioukas, S.G. 2010. Path planning for in-field navigation-aiding of service units. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 74(1), 80–90.
- Bryson, M., Reid, A., Ramos, F., Sukkarieh, S. 2010. Airborne vision-based mapping and classification of large farmland environments. *Journal of Field Robotics* 27(5): 632-655.
- Cohen, B., Edan, Y., Levi, A., Alchanatis, V. 2021. Early detection of grapevine downy mildew using thermal imaging. In *Precision Agriculture'21* (pp. 283-290). Wageningen Academic Publishers.
- Cohen Y., Roei I., Blank L., Goldshtein E., Eizenberg H. (2017) Spatial Spread of the Root Parasitic Weed *Phelipanche aegyptiaca* in Processing Tomatoes by Using Ecoinformatics and Spatial Analysis†. *Frontiers in Plant Science* 8. DOI: 10.3389/fpls.2017.00973.b
- Dunbabin, M., Grinham, A. (2010). Experimental evaluation of an autonomous surface vehicle for water quality and greenhouse gas emission monitoring. *Proc. IEEE Int. Con Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*: 5268-5274.
- Duso, C., Pozzebon, A., Capuzzo, C., Bisol, P. M., & Otto, S. (2003). Grape downy mildew spread and mite seasonal abundance in vineyards: evidence for the predatory mites *Amblyseius andersoni* and *Typhlodromus pyri*. *Biological Control*, 27(3), 229-241.
- Dusadeerungsikul, P. O., Nof, S. Y. 2019. A collaborative control protocol for agricultural robot routing with online adaptation. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 135, 456-466.
- Fountas, S., Mylonas, N., Malounas, I., Rodias, E., Hellmann Santos, C., Pekkeriet, E. 2020. Agricultural robotics for field operations. *Sensors*, 20(9), 2672.
- Gad, S., Y. Edan, Sandovsky, I. Harary T. Nacson, V. Alchanatis.. 2019. Early detection of maize and sunflower stress induced by chemicals' spraying. *European Conference on Precision Agriculture (ECPA 2019)*, Pages 279-285, Montpellier, France. *Precision Agriculture'19* (pp. 332-341). Wageningen Academic Publishers.
- Edan, Y., T. Flash, U.M. Peiper, I. Shmulevich, Y. Sarig. 1991. Near-minimum-time task planning algorithm for fruit-picking robots. *IEEE Transactions on Robotics and Automation* (1): 48-56.

- Edan, Y., K. Haghghi, R. Stroshine, M. Cardenas-Weber. 1992. Robot gripper analysis: Finite element modeling and optimization. *Applied Engineering in Agriculture* 8(4): 563-570.
- Edan, Y., G. E. Miles. 1994. Systems engineering of agricultural robot design. *IEEE Trans. on Systems, Man and Cybernetics* 24(8): 1259-1264.
- Edan, Y. 1995. Design of an autonomous agricultural robot. *The International Journal of Applied Intelligence* 5(1): 41-50.
- Edan, Y., V. Rogozin, T. Flash, G.E. Miles. 2000. Robotic Melon Harvesting. *IEEE Transactions on Robotics and Automation* 16(6): 831-834.
- Edan, Y., A. Bechar. 2020. ASIMP Robotic platform for ecological monitoring of insects populations. Ministry of Science Annual Report Year 1.
- izicovits, D., B. van Tuijl, S. Berman, Y. Edan. 2016. Integration of perception capabilities in gripper design using graspability maps. *BioSystems Engineering* 146: 98-113.
- Gad, S., Y. Edan, Sandovsky, I. Harary T. Nacson , V. Alchanatis.. 2019. Early detection of maize and sunflower stress induced by chemicals' spraying. *European Conference on Precision Agriculture (ECPA 2019)*, Pages 279-285, Montpellier, France. *Precision Agriculture'19* (pp. 332-341). Wageningen Academic Publishers.
- Gitzen R. A., Millspaugh J.J, Cooper A.B., Licht D.S., (2012) *Design and Analysis of Long-term Ecological Monitoring Studies* Cambridge University Press
- Goldshtein E., Cohen Y., Hetzroni A., Cohen Y., Soroker V. (2020) The spatiotemporal dynamics and range expansion of the red palm weevil in Israel. *Journal of Pest Science* 93:691-702. DOI: 10.1007/s10340-019-01176-8.
- Harel,B., R. van Essen, Y. Parmet, Y. Edan. 2020. Viewpoint analysis for maturity classification of sweet peppers. *Sensors* 20(13): 3783 [https://doi: 10.3390/s20133783](https://doi.org/10.3390/s20133783)
- Harel, B., Y. Parmet, Y. Edan, 2020. Maturity classification of sweet peppers using image datasets acquired in different times. *Computers in Industry* 121, 103274.
- Herricks, E. E., & Cairns Jr, J. (1982). Biological monitoring: part III—receiving system methodology based on community structure. *Water Research*, 16(2), 141-153.
- Jin, J., & Tang, L. (2010). Optimal coverage path planning for arable farming on 2D surfaces. *Transactions of ASABE*, 53(1), 283–295.
- Johnson, David A., Naffin, David J., Puhalla, Jeffrey S., Wellington, Carl K. 2009. Development and implementation of a team of robotic tractors for autonomous peat moss harvesting. *Journal of Field Robotics*, 23, 1–23.

- Ju, W. 2021, May. Application of autonomous navigation in robotics. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1906, No. 1, p. 012018). IOP Publishing.
- Kalantar, A., Edan, Y., Gur, A., Klapp, I. 2020. A deep learning system for single and overall weight estimation of melons using unmanned aerial vehicle images. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 178, 105748.
- Kalo, N., Edan, Y., A., Alchanatis, V. 2021. Detection of irrigation malfunctions based on thermal imaging. In *Precision Agriculture'21*. Wageningen Academic Publishers
- Kapach, K., Barnea, E., Mairon, R., Edan, Y., Ben-Shahar, O. 2012. Computer vision for fruit harvesting robots - State of the art and challenges ahead. *Intl. Journal of Computational Vision and Robotics* 3(1-2): 4-34.
- Krasnov H., Cohen Y., Goldshtein E., Mendelsohn O., Silberstein M., Gazit Y., Blank L. (2019) The effect of local and landscape variables on Mediterranean fruit fly dynamics in citrus orchards utilizing the ecoinformatics approach. *Journal of Pest Science* 92:453-463. DOI: 10.1007/s10340-018-1023-8.
- Kurtser, P., Edan, Y. 2018. Statistical models for fruit detectability: spatial and temporal analyses of sweet peppers. *Biosystems Engineering* 171: 272-289.
- Kurster, P., Y. Edan. 2020. Planning the sequence of tasks for harvesting robots. *Robots and Autonomous Systems* 103591.
- Kurtser, P., O. Ringdahl, N, Rotstein, R. Berenstein, Y. Edan. 2020. In-field grape cluster size assessment for vine yield estimation using a mobile robot and a consumer level RGB-D camera. *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters* 5(2): 2031-2038.
- Laykin, S., V. Alchanatis, Y. Edan. 2012. On-line multi-stage classifier for agriculture sorting systems. *Pattern Recognition* 45(7): 2843-2853.
- Linker, R., Blass, T. 2008. Path-planning algorithm for vehicles operating in orchards. *Biosystems Engineering*, 101(2), 152-160.
- Mazzetto, F., Calcante, A., Mena, A., Sacco, P. 2011. Test of ground-sensing devices for monitoring canopy vigour and downy mildew presence in vineyards: First qualitative results. *Journal of Agricultural Engineering*, 42(2), 1-10.
- Mohanty P.K., D.R. Parhi. 2013. Controlling the motion of an autonomous mobile robot using various techniques: a review, *J. Adv. Mech. Eng.* 24-39.

- Moysiadis, V., Tsolakis, N., Katikaridis, D., Sørensen, C. G., Pearson, S., Bochtis, D. 2020. Mobile Robotics in Agricultural Operations: A Narrative Review on Planning Aspects. *Applied Sciences*, 10(10), 3453.
- Muppala, C., Guruviah, V. 2020. Machine vision detection of pests, diseases and weeds: A review. *J. Phytol.*, 12, 9-19.
- Nair, A. S., Nof, S. Y., Bechar, A. 2021. Emerging Directions of Precision Agriculture and Agricultural Robotics. In *Innovation in Agricultural Robotics for Precision Agriculture* (pp. 177-210). Springer, Cham.
- Oliveira, L. F., Moreira, A. P., & Silva, M. F. (2021). Advances in agriculture robotics: A state-of-the-art review and challenges ahead. *Robotics*, 10(2), 52.
- Oppenheim, D. , Edan, Y., Shani, G. 2017. Detecting tomato flowers in greenhouses using computer vision. *International Journal of Computer and Information Engineering* 11(1): 104-109.
- Raja P., S. Pugazhenth. 2012, Optimal path planning of mobile robots: A review, *Int. J. Phys. Sci.* 7 (9) 1314–1320.
- Ram, T., Z. Wiesman, I. Parmet, Y. Edan. 2010. Olive oil content prediction models based on image processing. *Biosystems Engineering* 105(2): 221-232.
- Reggente, M., Mondini, A., Ferri, G., Mazzolai, B., Manzi, A., Gabelletti, M., Dario, P., Lilienthal, A. 2010. The DustBot system: Using mobile robots to monitor pollution in pedestrian area. *Chem. Eng.* 23:273-278.
- Ringdahl, O., Kurtser, P., Edan, Y. 2019. Evaluation of approach strategies for harvesting robots: Case study of sweet pepper harvesting. *Journal of Intelligent and Robotic Systems: Theory and Applications* 95: 149-164.
- Sandovsky, T., Y. Edan, S. Gad, A. Etzioni, T. Nacson, V. Alchanatis. 2019. Early detection of Fusarium infection in corn using spectral analysis. *European Conference on Precision Agriculture (ECPA 2019)*, Pages 339-346. Montpellier, France. *Precision Agriculture'19* (pp. 366-78). Wageningen Academic Publishers.
- Santos, L. C., Santos, F. N., Pires, E. S., Valente, A., Costa, P., Magalhães, S. 2020, April. Path planning for ground robots in agriculture: A short review. *IEEE International Conference on Autonomous Robot Systems and Competitions (ICARSC)* (pp. 61-66). IEEE.
- Schaeffer, D. J., Herricks, E. E., Kerster, H. W. 1998. Ecosystem health: I. Measuring ecosystem health. *Environmental Management*, 12(4), 445-455.

- Schor, N., A. Bechar, T. Ignat, A. Dombrovsky, Y. Elad, S. Berman 2016. Robotic Disease Detection in Greenhouses: Combined Detection of Powdery Mildew and Tomato Spotted Wilt Virus. *The IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters* 1(1): 354-360.
- Schor, N, S. Berman, T. Ignat, A. Dombrovsky, Y. Elad, A. Bechar 2017. Development of a robotic detection system for greenhouse pepper plants diseases. *Precision Agriculture* 18(3): 394-409.
- Seem, R. C., Magarey, P. A., McCloud, P. I., & Wachtel, M. F. (1985). A sampling procedure to detect grapevine downy mildew. *Phytopathology*, 75(11), 1252-1257.
- Shapiro, A., Korkidi, E., Demri, A. , Riemer, R., Edan, Y. Ben-Shahar, O. 2009. Toward Elevated Agrobotics: An Autonomous Field Robot for Spraying and Pollinating Date Palm Trees. Special Issue on Agricultural Robotics, *Journal of Field Robotics* 26 (6-7): 572-590.
- Sokolsky T., Cohen Y., Zahavi T., Sapir G., Sharon R. (2013) Potential efficiency of grapevine leafroll disease management strategies using simulation and real spatio-temporal disease infection data. *Australian Journal of Grape and Wine Research* 19:431-438.
- Sørensen, C. G., Bochtis, D. D. 2010. Conceptual model of fleet management in agriculture. *Biosystems Engineering*, 105, 41–50.
- Spolianski, R., Y. Edan, V. Alchanatis, U. Moallem, Y. Parmet, H. Honig, C, E. Maltz, A. Antler, I. Halachmi. 2016. Development of automatic body condition scoring using low-cost three dimensional kinect camera. *Journal of Dairy Science* 99: 7714-7723.
- Tahir, N., Brooker, G. 2009. Feasibility of UAV based optical tracker for tracking Australian plague locust. *Proc. Australasian Con Robotics and Automation (ACRA)*: 1-10.
- Qin Y.Q., D.B. Sun, N. Li, Y.G. Cen. 2017 Path planning for mobile robot using the particle swarm optimization with mutation operator, in: *International Conference on M*
- Vitzrabin, E., Y. Edan. 2016a. Changing Task Objectives for Improved Sweet Pepper Detection for Robotic Harvesting. *Robotics Automation Letters* 1(1): 575-584.
- Vitzrabin, E., Y. Edan. 2016b. Adaptive thresholding with fusion using a RGBD sensor for red sweet pepper detection. *BioSystems Engineering* 146: 45-56.
- Vougioukas, S. G. Agricultural robotics. 2019. *Annual review of control, robotics, and autonomous systems* 2: 365-392.
- Wadhams, P., Wilkinson, J. P., McPhail, S. D. (2006). A new view of the underside of arctic sea ice. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 33(4): 1-5.

Yehoshua, A. 2021. Sampling strategies for an ecological monitoring robot. Final project, Industrial Engineering, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev.

Zemmour, E., P. Kurtser, Y. Edan. 2019. Automatic parameter tuning for adaptive thresholding in fruit detection. *Sensors* 19(9): 2130.

Zhang H., J. Butzke, M. Likhachev. 2012, Combining global and local planning with guarantees on completeness, in: *IEEE Intl. Conference on Robotics and Automation*: 4500–4506.

שמואל, ל. 2018. דינאמיקה של אקרית אדומה מצויה (*Tetranychus urticae*) בבתי רשת פלפל ואפיון תצורת ניטור בזמן ובמרחב, הפקולטה לחקלאות, רחובות, האוניברסיטה העברית, ירושלים.